

SROC Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress

Abstract book

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Updated ESTRO Core Curriculum for medical physicists-what is new that we need to know

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Abstract

First guidelines on medical physicist roles, responsibilities, education and training was published more than thirty years ago, but since then, the profession has evolved to many sub-specialties including radiotherapy, nuclear medicine and radiology. Latest technological developments in radiotherapy, as well as new EU regulation that established medical physics expert, required urgent update of existing guidelines, brought in 2011. New core curriculum was brought by a workgroup established in 2019 and represented by 27 medical physicists representing EFOMP, ESTRO as well as national societies and international experts.

The training period should be 4 years, with total of 240 ECTS (European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System). The competency based education has been reinforced by introducing CanMEDs framework.

The updated curriculum includes stereotactic, MR guided and adaptive RT, particle therapy, automation, artificial intelligence, and also emphasis has been given to quality and risk management. The research project at the end ensures proper preparation of MPE resident for their central role in science and innovation in radiation therapy.

The ESTRO-EFOMP core curriculum 2022 (3rd revised edition) is aiming to define a baseline standard for the education and training Medical Physics Experts (MPE) in Radiotherapy.

- provide a framework for national regulatory bodies to guide their own curriculum development
- contribute to harmonization in Europe in order to facilitate cross-border mobility of professionals
- improve the standard of training across Europe

Keywords: medical physics, guidelines, education, training

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